

Table 1. A description of the parameters and their values used in this study.

Parameter	Description (units)	Default Value
g	Resource, R , intrinsic growth rate (time^{-1})	5
K	Resource, R , carrying capacity (biomass)	50
c_{NR}	Consumption rate of IG prey, N , on resource, R (time^{-1})	Varied: 0.5 when “equal competitors” or 1 when “prey superior”
c_{PR}	Consumption rate of resource-eating predator morph, P , on resource, R (time^{-1})	0.5
c_{ZN}	Consumption rate of top predator morph, Z , on IG prey, N (time^{-1})	0.5
c_{ZP}	Consumption rate of top predator morph, Z , on resource-eating predator morph, P (time^{-1})	0.5
e_{NR}	Conversion efficiency of IG prey, N , on resource, R (biomass of N /unit R consumed)	0.5
e_{PR}	Conversion efficiency of resource-eating predator morph, P , on resource, R (biomass of P /unit R consumed)	0.5
e_{ZN}	Conversion efficiency of top predator morph, Z , on IG prey, N (biomass of Z /unit N consumed)	0.5
e_{ZP}	Conversion efficiency of top predator morph, Z , on resource-eating predator morph, P (biomass of Z /unit P consumed)	0.5
d_N	IG prey, N , mortality rate (time^{-1})	0.5
d_P	Resource-eating predator morph, P , mortality rate (time^{-1})	0.5
d_Z	Top predator morph, Z , mortality rate (time^{-1})	0.5
u_{RZ}	Switching rate from top predator morph, Z , to resource-eating predator morph, P ($\text{density}^{-1}\text{time}^{-1}$)	0.5

u_{NP}	Switching rate from resource-eating predator morph, P , to top predator morph, Z , dependent on IG prey, N , population (density ⁻¹ time ⁻¹)	0.5
u_{PP}	Switching rate from resource-eating predator morph, P , to top predator morph, Z , dependent on conspecific resource-eating predator morph, P , population (density ⁻¹ time ⁻¹)	0.5
s	Preference parameter (unitless)	Varied: 0.3 for heterospecific preference, 0.5 for no preference, 0.7 for preferential cannibalism